

Oxomolybdenum(V) and Oxomolybdenum(VI) Complexes of Some New Dithiocarbamates

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Synthesis and characterisation of μ -oxo-di [*bis*(dithiocarbamato)oxomolybdenum(V)] and *bis*(dithiocarbamato)dioxomolybdenum(VI) with some new dithiocarbamato ligands of the type $RR'NCS_2^-$, where $R = C_6H_5, CH_3$ and $R' = H, CH_3, C_2H_5, C_2H_5^+$ and C_6H_5, CH_3 , have been reported.

MOLYBDENUM is an important trace element in living organisms. Oxomolybdenum(V) and oxomolybdenum(VI) have recently been proposed as models for molybdenum coordination in enzymes^{1,2}. In the present paper we report synthesis and characterization of some oxomolybdenum(V) complexes of the type $Mo_2O_3(dtc)_4$ and oxomolybdenum(VI) complexes of the type $MoO_2(dtc)_2$ with a series of new dithiocarbamate ligands I, viz., (i) benzylmethyl dithiocarbamate (BzMe-dtc), I_a; (ii) benzylethyl dithiocarbamate (BzEt-dtc), I_b; (iii) benzylisopropyl dithiocarbamate (BzisoPr-dtc), I_c and (iv) dibenzyl dithiocarbamate (Bz₂-dtc), I_d.

(a) $R = CH_3$, BzMe-dtc; (b) $R = C_2H_5$, BzEt-dtc;
(c) $R = i-C_3H_7$, BzisoPr-dtc and (d) $R = C_6H_5$, Bz₂-dtc.

Moore and Larson³ had earlier reported difficulty in isolating pure oxomolybdenum(VI) complexes with larger and branched chain alkyl groups, viz., isopropyl and benzyl.

Experimental

A. Preparations: Sodium, potassium or ammonium salts of the dithiocarbamates were prepared by earlier described methods⁴.

(i) $Mo_2O_3(dtc)_4$: For preparing the complexes of this type solution of the dithiocarbamate ligand (0.004 mol, aqueous or aquo-ethanolic) was added to a freshly prepared aqueous solution of $(NH_4)_2MoO_4$ (0.002 mol) with stirring. The complexes were thrown out in each case, which were filtered, washed with water and vacuum dried over P_2O_5 .

(ii) $MoO_2(dtc)_2$: For preparing the complexes of this type a solution containing sodium acetate

(2 g), $Na_2MoO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ (0.010 mol) and the dithiocarbamate ligand (3.65 g; 0.010 mole) in 250 ml of 50% ethyl alcohol was acidified by dropwise addition of 2 M nitric acid with stirring at 0° to adjust the pH to ~5.5. The complex precipitated out in each case which was filtered out, washed with cold water and dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 . The dried solid was recrystallised from CH_2Cl_2 -petroleum ether/cyclohexane.

The complexes are soluble in $CHCl_3$ and CH_2Cl_2 . An unpurified sample attained a slight purple tinge in a few days, probably getting reduced to molybdenum(V) species. The recrystallised sample was found to be stable over a period of one year.

B. Physical measurements: Magnetic susceptibility measurements on solid complexes were made by Gouy method using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as calibrant

$$(\chi_g = 16.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cgsu})$$

Infrared spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 621 and Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometers. Visible spectra were recorded on Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

A. $Mo_2O_3(dtc)_4$: All the complexes are diamagnetic. $Mo_2O_3(dtc)_4$ complexes are crystallographically^{5,7} known to have two $MoO(dtc)_2$ units joined by a bridging oxygen atom, the $Mo=O$ bonds of both units being on the same side. In mono-oxygen bridged complexes spin pairing occurs via the bridging oxygen atom, which leads to diamagnetism⁸⁻¹¹.

The visible spectra of the complexes show two strong bands around 24000 cm^{-1} and 19000 cm^{-1} (Table 1). The 24000 cm^{-1} band is assignable to $L \rightarrow M$ charge transfer^{3,12,13}. In $Mo_2O_3(Me_2dtc)_4$ and $Mo_2O_3(Et_2dtc)_4$ this absorption occurs⁸ at 2000 cm^{-1} higher than in the present

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION AND λ_{max} OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Compound*	Colour	m. p. °C	Found (Calcd.) C%	Found (Calcd.) H%	Found (Calcd.) N%	Found (Calcd.) Mo%	λ_{max} (cm ⁻¹) in CH ₂ Cl ₂ (log ϵ)
1.	Mo ₂ O ₃ (Bz ₂ -dtc) ₄	purple violet	84° dec.	54.53 (54.22)	4.00 (4.22)	3.90 (4.12)	14.83 (14.45)	24100 (3.48) 19010 (3.82)
2.	Mo ₂ O ₃ (BzMe-dtc) ₄	purple violet	96°	41.80 (42.19)	3.72 (3.90)	5.00 (5.47)	18.98 (18.47)	24630 (3.40) 19080 (3.44)
3.	Mo ₂ O ₃ (BzEt-dtc) ₄	purple violet	112° dec.	44.00 (44.45)	4.60 (4.44)	4.88 (5.19)	17.50 (17.77)	23360 (3.10) 19080 (3.01)
4.	Mo ₂ O ₃ (Bz isoPr-dtc) ₄	purple violet	89° dec.	45.84 (46.48)	4.80 (4.93)	4.80 (4.93)	17.00 (16.89)	24210 (3.37) 19080 (3.44)
5.	MoO ₂ (Bz ₁ -dtc) ₂	yellow	157° dec.	53.00 (53.58)	4.30 (4.17)	3.80 (4.17)	14.55 (14.28)	27550 (3.99) 26320 (4.00) 24100 sh (3.62)
6.	MoO ₂ (BzMe-dtc) ₂	orange yellow	153-155° dec.	40.90 (41.54)	3.70 (3.85)	4.90 (5.39)	18.32 (18.45)	26320 (3.62)
7.	MoO ₂ (BzEt-dtc) ₂	orange yellow	68-70°	43.28 (43.87)	4.08 (4.38)	5.32 (5.11)	17.30 (17.51)	23810 (3.21)
8.	MoO ₂ (Bz isoPr-dtc) ₂	yellow	161° dec.	45.60 (45.84)	4.78 (4.86)	5.02 (4.86)	16.30 (16.65)	23310 (3.09)

* ligands abbreviated as in the text.

complexes. This suggests that benzyl derivatives are better reducing agents than dialkyldithiocarbamates, as also is evidenced from the fact that the Mo(VI) complexes of the present ligands are difficult to prepare. Moore and Larsen³ have earlier observed that S→Mo charge-transfer in xanthate complexes appear at 6000 cm⁻¹ below that of the corresponding dithiocarbamate complexes and have suggested that xanthates are much better reducing agents than dithiocarbamates. Also no Mo(VI) complex of xanthates is known.

The 19000 cm⁻¹ band is characteristic of the linear Mo-O-Mo bridge and is assigned to a transition terminating in the antibonding component of the three centre Mo-O-Mo bond^{2,14,15}.

All the Mo₂O₃(dtc)₄ complexes show an earlier reported^{2,15} behaviour that the colour of their CH₂Cl₂ solution changes from purple through orange to yellow on standing. This colour change is accompanied with weakening of the 19000 cm⁻¹ band which finally disappears. The phenomenon has now been proved definitively to be due to the following equilibrium in solution^{2,14,15,21}:

All Mo₂O₃(dtc)₄ complexes show one strong band in the range 920-935 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to both symmetric and antisymmetric terminal Mo=O stretching¹⁶ modes (ν_1^s and ν_2^s). The above assignment is based on the work of Newton and McDonald, who studied the infrared spectra of ¹⁶O and ¹⁸O analogs of Mo₂O₃(dtc)₄ to conclude that a single band at 945 ± 15 cm⁻¹ represents both symmetric and antisymmetric Mo-O_t stretching frequencies¹⁶. Spectra of all the complexes also show a medium intensity band at 420 cm⁻¹ due

to symmetric Mo-O-Mo stretching mode¹⁶. The antisymmetric Mo-O-Mo stretching band¹⁶ could be observed only in Mo₂O₃(BzMe-dtc)₄ (at 742 cm⁻¹), while in all other complexes strong ligand absorptions obscure this band.

A strong band in the range 1470-1505 cm⁻¹ is due to CN stretching mode. This band is observed in the range 1510-1550 cm⁻¹ in the corresponding dialkyl derivatives³. The observed lowering in energy of this absorption in the present complexes may be explained as follows. The presence of the benzyl group in the present complexes exerts an inductive effect, -I, by withdrawing electrons into the π -ring system of benzene. This effect would decrease the double bond character of the CN bond.

The $\nu_{(C-S)}^s$ and $\nu_{(C-S)}^a$ stretching frequencies in our complexes have been observed as strong bands in the regions 954-985 cm⁻¹ and 688-700 cm⁻¹ respectively. Medium to strong bands in the range 345-400 cm⁻¹ are observed due to Mo-S stretching mode^{2,19,16}.

B. MoO₂(dtc)₂: Moore and Larson³ prepared dimethyl and diethyl derivatives by acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid, using the method of Malatesta¹⁶ and reported that poor results were obtained with dithiocarbamates containing higher alkyl groups. The di-*n*-propyl derivative was prepared by using dilute nitric acid and the di-*n*-butyl derivative was prepared by oxidising the intermediate product with *t*-butyl hydroperoxide. The tendency to form a purple tar, believed to be the crude Mo(V) complex, increased with the increasing size of the alkyl group and pure Mo(VI) complexes with alkyl groups larger than *n*-butyl group could not be isolated. This instability is probably related

to the decreased electron releasing ability of the higher alkyl groups. They also could not prepare di-iso-propyl derivative. It is quite encouraging that we got analytically pure yellow benzylisopropyl derivative, $\text{MoO}_2(\text{Bz isoPr-dtc})_2$, using 1M HNO_3 and acetate buffer¹⁰ at 0-5°. In the case of $\text{MoO}_2(\text{Bz}_2\text{-dte})_2$ and $\text{MoO}_2(\text{BzMe-dtc})_2$, the above method of preparation always resulted into the yellow Mo(VI) complex contaminated with some amount of purple coloured Mo(V). These two complexes and also $\text{MoO}_2(\text{BzEt-dtc})_2$ were, therefore, prepared in aqueous ethanolic medium, taking advantage of the fact that Mo(VI) has an edge over Mo(V) in the presence of the organic solvents^{2,13}.

The electronic spectral bands for the complexes are listed in Table 1. All these bands are due to $\text{Mo} \leftarrow \text{S}$ charge-transfer absorptions^{18,19}.

All the complexes show two strong bands one each in the regions $903\text{-}910\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $870\text{-}875\text{ cm}^{-1}$, assignable to the two $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ stretching modes¹⁶. The presence of two bands is consistent with the cis-dioxo structure of the MoO_2 group, which has been confirmed by crystallography for several $\text{MoO}_2(\text{dte})_2$ complexes^{6,20}.

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References

1. P. W. SCHNEIDER, D. C. BRAVARD, J. W. McDONALD and W. E. NEWTON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 8640.
2. W. E. NEWTON, J. L. CORBIN, D. C. BRAVARD, J. E. SEARLES and J. W. McDONALD, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, 13, 1100.
3. F. W. MOORE and M. L. LARSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, 6, 998.
4. M. DELEPINE, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1908, 3, 643.
5. C. D. GARNER, N. C. HOWLADER, F. E. MABBS, A. T. MCPHAIL, K. D. ONAN and P. M. GROSS, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton*, 1979, 962.
6. T. E. WELFF, J. M. BORG, P. P. POWER, K. D. HODGSON and R. H. HOLM, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, 19, 430.
7. L. RICHARD, J. ESTIENNE, P. KARAGIANUDIS, P. TOLEDANO, A. MITCHELL and R. WEISS, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1974, 3, 277.
8. A. B. BLAKE, F. A. COTTON and J. S. WOOD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 3024.
9. F. A. COTTON and R. M. WING, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 6, 867.
10. B. BLUES, D. H. BROWN, R. G. PERKINS and D. J. P. STEWART, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1974, 8, 67.
11. L. NATKANIEC, M. RUDOLF and B. J. TRZEBIATOWSKA, *Theoret. Chim. Acta*, 1973, 28, 193.
12. R. N. JOWITT and P. C. H. MITCHELL, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 1702.
13. A. T. CASEY, D. J. MACKAY, R. L. MARTIN and A. H. WHITE, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1972, 25, 477.
14. C. D. GARNER, N. C. HOWLADER, F. E. MABBS, A. T. MCPHAIL, K. D. ONAN and P. M. GROSS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, 15, 2612.
15. A. B. BLAKE, F. A. COTTON and J. S. WOOD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 3024.
16. W. E. NEWTON and J. W. McDONALD, *J. Less. Common Metals*, 1977, 54, 51.
17. L. MALATESTA, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1939, 69, 952.
18. C. K. JORGENSEN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1962, 24, 1511.
19. G. GOTTOW, A. FRAUKE and A. MILLER, *Naturwiss.*, 1965, 52, 428.
20. L. RICHARD, J. ESTIENNE, P. KARAGIANUDIS, P. TOLEDANO, A. MITCHELL and R. WEISS, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1974, 3, 277.
21. T. MATSUDE, K. TANAKA and T. TANAKA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, 18, 454.